

THE HYDROGEN-OXYGEN COMBINATION IN A SIEMEN'S OZONISER

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Gaseous mixtures of hydrogen and oxygen were subjected to the electric discharge in a Siemen's ozoniser. Gas pressures up to 50 cm. of Hg and applied potentials of 2000-4000 volts were employed. The current-potential relationship as well as the variation of the gas pressure with time were investigated for different values of applied potential, $H_2 : O_2$ ratio, and total initial gas pressure. The sudden and large changes in the secondary current looked for at the threshold potentials were only noticed in systems where the initial gas pressure was below 10 cm. of Hg.

The union of hydrogen and oxygen as well as the decomposition of water vapour when subjected to electric discharges has been extensively studied by several workers. Kirkby (*Phil. Mag.*, 1907, 13, 299; 1905, 171, 185; *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1911, 85, A, 151) made a critical investigation of the hydrogen-oxygen reaction in a discharge tube and correlated the amount of water formed with the gas pressure and the different electrical factors. Finch and others (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1931, 133, A, 173; 1930, 129, A, 672; 1926, 111, A, 257; 1927, 116, A, 529) studied the cathodic combustion of hydrogen and oxygen mixtures at sputtering and non-sputtering cathodes. Löb (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1906, 12, 282; *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 1517) reported the formation of hydrogen peroxide on subjecting moist carbon dioxide to silent electric discharge. Comanducci (*Gazzetta*, 1909, 40, 600) investigated the effect of the silent electric discharge on various gaseous mixtures including that of hydrogen and oxygen. The reaction between the last two gases was studied in the electrodeless discharge by Rodebush and co-workers (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1937, 41, 283) and in the silent electric discharge by Fisher and Wolf (*Ber.*, 1911, 44, 2956; *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1914, 20, 204). Chattock and Tyndall (*Phil. Mag.*, 1908, 14, 24) studied the changes of pressure which accompany point-discharges through hydrogen containing oxygen and nitrogen. The reverse reaction namely the decomposition of water vapour was also studied by numerous workers (Keanbaum, *Compt. rend.*, 1910, 181, 319; Linder, *Phys. Rev.*, 1931, 38, 679; Urey and Lavin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 3290; Rodebush and Wahl, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1933, 1, 696; Langmuir, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 28, 1357) under conditions obtaining in different regions of a discharge tube and also in various other forms of electric discharge. The chemical effects of electrical discharges with special reference to ionisation and the reaction velocity have been dealt with at length by Poma (*Gazzetta*, 1921, 2, 58), Briner (*J. chim. phys.*, 1915, 13, 18; 1914, 12, 526, 534), Lunt (*Nature*, 1936, 137, 404; Elliot, Joshi and Lunt, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, 23, 57), Joshi and co-workers (*ibid.*, 1927, 23, 227; 1929, 26, 108, 118, 137); Joshi and Sharma (*J. chim. phys.*, 1934, 31, 511); Finch and others (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1931, 133, A, 173; 1934, 143, A, 482); Emieus and Kennedy (*Phil. Mag.*, 1934, 18, 874); Bouлинд (*Phil. Mag.*, 1934, 18, 909); Max Le Blanc and Davies (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1908, 14, 361), Susumu Miyamoto (*J. Sci. Hiroshima Univ. Japan*, 1932, 2, 218). Investigations on the passage of silent electric discharge through nitric oxide and through mixtures of hydrogen and chlorine which were conducted by Joshi and co-workers (not published) showed that gradual increases of the secondary voltage applied to the reaction mixture in the ozoniser caused

sudden and large change in the secondary current at the values of the threshold potentials. The work described below was undertaken with a view to examining the nature of variation of the secondary current and gas pressure with the applied potentials and the duration of the discharge in the case of hydrogen and oxygen mixtures.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fig. 1 is a diagrammatic representation of the general disposition of the apparatus employed which is essentially similar to the one used by Joshi and co-workers (*loc. cit.*). Circulation of water through the outer jacket tube J served to maintain the temperature of the reacting gaseous mixture contained in the annular space RC of the ozoniser constant during the passage of the electric discharge. The energy needed for maintaining

FIG. 1

- dd—Drying tubes packed with CaCl_2 or P_2O_5 .
 R_1 & R_2 —Gas reservoirs for H_2 & O_2
 RC—Annular space of the ozoniser.
 C_1 & C_2 —Electrode chambers with conducting liquid.
 J—Jacket for cold water circulation.
 M—Hg manometer.
 T—Tipler pump.
 M_1 & M_2 —Hg reservoirs.
 T_1 & T_2 —Secondaries of the transformer.
 S_1 to S_4 —Vacuum stop-cock.

the electric discharge was supplied by means of a rotary converter and an oil-immersed step-up transformer with a maximum range of 40,000 volts, connected through suitable resistances and a switch. The secondary terminals T_1 and T_2 of the transformer were connected to two strips of metal immersed in the electrolyte solution contained in the

electrode chambers C_2 and C_1 respectively. The terminal T_2 was also earthed. The current flowing through the reaction chamber could be measured by means of a sensitive microammeter placed in the earthing circuit. The actual potential applied could be varied at will by regulating the resistance in the primary circuit of the transformer and its exact value was computed from the reading of the voltmeter placed across the primary circuit and the transformer-ratio. This experimental arrangement enabled single phase alternating current at any potential to be applied to the reaction mixture and the corresponding gas pressure or secondary current to be read from time to time. The entire apparatus was made of glass and ground glass joints or rubber tubing for connecting the different pieces of the apparatus were avoided. Only good quality vacuum grease was used for the stop-cocks. After thorough exhaustion of the air in the apparatus by means of a Cenco Hyvac and the Töpler pumps, the resulting vacuum measured by means of a McLeod gauge was found to be of the order of 5×10^{-4} cm. of Hg, and this was considered sufficient for purposes of these studies.

The following are the dimensions of the reaction chamber used :—

Inner diameter of the inner tube	...	1.3 cm.
Outer diameter of the inner tube	...	1.5 "
Thickness of the wall	...	0.1 "
Inner diameter of the outer tube	...	1.8 "
Outer diameter of the outer tube	...	2.1 "
Thickness of the wall	...	0.15 "
Mean width of the annular space	...	0.15 "
Mean length of the annular space	...	27.45 "
Volume of the annular space excluding that of the connecting capillaries	...	22.4 c.c.

Taking the usual precautions, the gas reservoirs R_1 and R_2 were first filled with pure dry hydrogen and oxygen respectively, to serve as stock for all the experiments. The required quantities of the two gases were then enclosed in the annular space RC of the ozoniser, so as to give a mixture having the desired $H_2 : O_2$ ratio and the total initial gas pressure. During the whole course of the experiment, and in particular when recording the reading of the manometer, care was taken to see that the mercury in the left limb was always maintained just touching the tip of the glass index G inside the limb. This was done by raising or lowering the mercury reservoir M_1 . The difference in height between the mercury levels in the two limbs gave the pressure of the gaseous mixtures under investigation.

After switching on the current, the resistances in the primary circuit of the transformer were carefully regulated in order to maintain the secondary voltage at the desired value and the discharge was allowed to pass for the necessary length of time. The pressure reading of the manometer was recorded at regular intervals of time, and so too the micro-ammeter readings.

In those series of experiments, which were carried out with a view to examining the current-voltage relationship, the general procedure adopted as a rule was to start with a low applied potential and gradually increase it to about 4000 volts in a number of steps, recording at the same time the micro-ammeter reading at each step. Also before raising

the potential to a new value, the reaction mixture was maintained under the existing potential for a time-interval of about one to three minutes in order to enable any falling tendency of the gas pressure under the influence of the electric discharge, which was indicative of the progress of the chemical reaction, to be noted.

DISCUSSION

Curves I to XI shown in Fig. 2 give the variations of the gas pressure with time in a few typical experiments. The figures within brackets represent the total initial gas pressure, p , the hydrogen: oxygen ratio, r , the applied potential, V , respectively. In curve I the applied potential was 2,700 volts during the first 78 minutes, but it was

FIG. 2

dimished to 2,500 volts for the remaining period. In curves, II, IV, V, VI, VIII, IX and X, the potential was gradually raised to the values indicated against them after a brief intermittent trial at lower voltages, and the time and manometer readings were started after the respective voltages were brought to their final values. In curve III, the actual initial gas pressure was 41.95 cm., but after a few brief trials lasting for nearly 13 minutes at voltages ranging up to 2,600, the discharge was interrupted for 24 hours. At the end of the 24 hours' period of interruption the gas pressure fell down to 36 cm. This is indicated by the dotted portion of the curve III. The discharge was recommenced at 2,600 volts and continued for 96 minutes, and the corresponding pressure-time readings were plotted to give the continuous portion of the curve III. In curve VII, V was maintained at 2,500 volts during the first one hour. The discharge was then interrupted for 4 hours and continued again under 2,400 volts for 80 minutes. In curve XI, V was maintained at 4,000 volts right from the start.

The pressure-time curves VIII, IX, and XI and to a less extent VI and VII, shown in Fig. 2, indicate that a steady and rapid combination of the two gases takes place in the earlier part of the duration of the discharge, and that the reactions later tend towards an equilibrium state, represented by the horizontal shape of the final portion of the curves. The actual time required for the reaction to attain the equilibrium state depends upon several factors, chiefly, the total gas pressure at the start and the applied voltage. Within the scope of the ranges examined in these investigations, it appears from the slopes of curves that lower initial gas pressures and / or higher applied potentials are favourable for a rapid attainment of the final state. This fact is very clearly brought out by the curves IV and XI representing 2,300 and 4,000 volts respectively. It is also to be naturally expected that appreciably lower applied voltages are accompanied by smaller initial rates of reaction, as is borne out by curve X (Fig. 2) obtained for 1,800 volts. Curve VIII (Fig. 2) discloses an important point worthy of note. Observations of the secondary current values which were simultaneously recorded showed that the maximum current flowing through the reaction mixture exactly synchronised with the maximum rate of fall of the gas pressure, noticed at 27'. This last was of course followed by a sudden slowing down of the reaction velocity leading to the steady equilibrium condition. It was also noticed that the characteristic sizzling sound of the discharge became very low and almost inaudible at the 32'-33' interval. Another interesting finding which has resulted from a careful examination of curve IX (Fig. 2) might also be mentioned here; namely that, on the assumption that the reaction had attained the final equilibrium state at 63' after the start, when the unimolecular velocity constants were calculated from

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t} \cdot \log \frac{a}{a-x},$$

very concordant values for k were obtained. Values of $\log (a-x)$ plotted against the time yielded a straight line graph. Similar results were not obtained for the other cases studied.

An examination of the variation with time of the secondary current passing through the reaction mixture under a constant applied potential was also made and the curves I, II, III, IV, V shown in Fig. 3 were obtained. While it appears from these that as a result of the progress of the chemical reactions taking place in the ozoniser the magnitude of the secondary current goes on decreasing, for some time at least, with the dura-

tion of the discharge, it is to be noted that the rate of the decrease, unlike that of the gas pressure referred to above, is not quite consistent and is perhaps of a different significance

FIG. 3

Scale A refers to curve G and scale B to curves I to V.

The figures within the brackets indicate the initial gas pressure, p , the $H_2:O_2$ ratio, r , and the applied potential, V , respectively.

altogether. In fact, in certain experiments of this series, it was even found that the current instead of showing a fall in the manner indicated by the curves I to V of Fig. 3, continued to remain more or less at the same value, only fluctuating within narrow limits. Obviously there are several factors contributing to the actual observed values of the current. It is not unlikely that the various direct and reverse reactions involved in the formation and decomposition of water vapour, ozone and hydrogen peroxide side by side constitute factors of considerable complexity detracting from the usefulness of the current measurements for the purpose of studying the reaction-kinetics. Besides, even in the cases where such complicating factors are absent, any attempt at a quantitative study of the chemical kinetics on the basis of the current-measurements seems unwarranted on account of the extraordinary precautions required to be taken in purifying the gases under investigation, in eliminating effectively the role of the last traces of water vapour or other adsorbed gases, etc. Furthermore, the difficulty of accurately controlling the primary voltage within narrow limits for an appreciable period of time stands in the way of maintaining correctly and exactly a constant secondary potential.

The general variation of the secondary current with applied voltage for hydrogen-oxygen mixtures is indicated by the curve G (Fig. 3). Since it was found that the

reactions proceeded with measurable velocities at or below 2,600 volts, higher potentials were not applied in most of these experiments. The initial gas pressures in the different

FIG. 4.

The figures within the brackets indicate the total initial gas pressure, p and the $H_2:O_2$ ratio, r , respectively.

cases ranged from 3 to 50 cm. Hg and the $H_2:O_2$ ratios were varied from 1:1 to 3:1. The micro-ammeter readings were noted at each stage and the applied potential was increased and these were plotted against the values of the latter. Some typical curves obtained are shown in Figs. 4 and 5. It will be seen from the curves I, II, III and IV (Fig. 4) which refer to systems of pressure over 27 cm. Hg., that the expected and looked for large and sudden increases of the current values at or near the threshold potentials are not found. At pressures below 27 cm. Hg., while the existence of such a feature is not very clearly noticeable (see curves V to IX of Fig. 4) there is a distinct tendency in that direction. In the case of curves X to XVI of Fig. 5 it is distinctly discernible and it appears to be particularly so at the lowest pressures studied, namely in the range 3.7 to 10 cm. Hg. A discussion of the significance and implications of these results will be made in a separate communication.

FIG. 5

The figures within the brackets indicate the total initial gas pressure p , and $H_2 : O_2$ ratio, r , respectively.

The author desires, in conclusion to express his sincere thanks to Prof. S. S. Joshi, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Benares Hindu University, for suggesting this work and for his kind guidance and interest in this investigation. The laboratory facilities afforded by the Benares Hindu University for conducting this work are also gratefully remembered by the author.

This author's thanks are due to Dr. L. C. Verman, Director Physical Laboratories who gave his kind permission to communicate this paper.

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Received January 27, 1945.